

Using the BRICS People-to-People Exchange and Cultural Indigenous Management to Extract Value from the Big Data Environment

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Governments within the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, & South Africa) grouping should build on existing relationships among themselves to develop laws that promote the sharing and exchange of data using Indigenous management concepts so that communities can extract value from their Indigenous big data environment. Big data has the potential to change the whole world; however, the adoption of big data practices and data usage is centered more on cultural exchange than on technology. The problem is that big data is being approached based on available data stocks (volume) instead of looking for specific, valuable data needed in operations. This topic should be approached using BRICS people-to-people exchange and cultural Indigenous management concepts such as *guanxi* (China), *jugaad* (India), *blat* (Russia), and *ubuntu* (South Africa) that are built on personal relations and organisation relations to exchange favours. This is the key needed to extract value from data in this fifth industrial revolution. This paper explores how countries within BRICS, which have unique histories and practices of conducting business as indigenous groupings, can use the BRICS people-to-people exchange cultural principle to extract value from their own data. A case study and purposive sampling were used to investigate the problem. A localised study comprising 23 participants and a focus group was conducted. What emerged is that there are no clear frameworks and a lack of relevant skills to exploit opportunities in the current big data environment. A framework to overcome this challenge and exploit opportunities was produced from this study. It is now time to have a big data value extraction license for countries within BRICS.

Keywords: People-to-people, Indigenous management, big data environment, big data framework, data exchange

Big data is believed to be a key resource in the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Many organisations are yet to derive tangible value from them, Bello-Orgaz, Jung, and Camacho (2016) listed the characteristics of big data as volume, variety, velocity, veracity, and value. The problem appears to be giving too much attention to the

volume characteristic of big data, often at the expense of the other four characteristics, particularly the value characteristic, which is concerned with extracting value from the data. Data analysis, which is rendered a mission impossible due to various data structures that range from structured data, semi-structured data, to unstructured data from various sources (Banumathi & Aloysius, 2017). Veracity deals with uncertainty, which means the data may need to be cleaned before use (Shukla, Yadav, Kumar, & Muhuri, 2020). Hardware capacity must then address the velocity part and the speed of execution (Ghasemaghahi & Calic, 2020). Handling volume remains a major challenge; however, there is now a significant improvement in this area due to cloud computing. Value attracts everyone's attention, hence the hype in various fields of study (Demchenko et al., 2013).

What initially triggered this hype was the amount of data that was being generated in Google, Yahoo, Facebook, and X (Fan & Bifet, 2015). Many people still think of these sources whenever they hear the word big data because "The big word in 'big data' itself defines the volume." (Kata, Wazid, & Goudar, 2013). What is important to note is that big data is not only related to volume, but other characteristics of big data are also equally important (Acciarini et al., 2023). The fact that volume puts pressure on hardware, programs, and the need for analytical skills. Those in the technical sciences have taken the lead and made strides in developing tools to harness and analyse the data. In that aspect, Information systems researchers have dominated big data research to the extent of becoming specialists with few connections to other fields, thereby widening

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the gap between technical and social, and the ability to think as a community (Grover et al., 2020). They have often used technical theories such as the UTAUT and DOI to look at the big data problem, yet big data cuts across various fields. This resulted in an uncoordinated approach to the big data problem. Grindrod (2017) coined it science versus commercial and encouraged everyone to focus on extracting rather than competing.

Some fields take keen interest in value, but they face ethical and legal challenges, and lack of appropriate frameworks because they try to use theories from the Information Systems field to look at the big data problem. Others argue that the legal framework is not yet ready, so they focus more on the legal aspects because big data cannot be easily accessed without stepping into legal, ethical, and risk issues. Glosson (2016) highlighted that the major problem is that data can cross country boundaries, making it difficult to apply the laws of the country of origin. *“That is why, there is no doubt, that policymakers must create favourable conditions to apply these technologies safely and beneficial to regulators, innovators, businesses, and customers”* (Gromova & Ivanc, 2020, p.13). However, literature dealing with the human factor in Information technology security, particularly in big data environments, is fragmented, and this has resulted in splintered knowledge, creating confusion for policy makers (Chatterjee, Kar, & Mustafa, 2021).

Problem Statement

Many organisations, including the BRICS, have aspired to extract value from big data. The problem is that it is being approached from the security point of view to protect the data instead of putting policies that promote the sharing of data. Scientific theories have been used to look at the problem without incorporating theories from other social fields. *“The strongest contribution to knowledge will come when we harness both the power of big data and rigorous methods and theories from social science”* (Monroe et al., 2014, p.74). Organisations and Countries have been lining up to exploit opportunities from the big data environment without giving due attention to the doctrine of extraterritoriality, the politics around the data, data ownership, the elements of risk, and ethical and legal considerations (Rena, 2024). They then face a roadblock and abandon any ambition of extracting value from the data. Countries within the BRICS grouping are poised to overcome these challenges if they adopt a framework that addresses these problems by involving theories from other fields to craft laws that promote the exchange and usage of data. The issue of a lack of a framework to adopt big data in organisations has been insufficiently investigated and remained unanswered for a long time (Olszak & Mach-Król, 2018). Therefore, lack of an appropriate framework, lack of an agreed code of ethics, and lack of appropriate theories from other fields to look at the big data problem are what is hindering the BRICS nations from realizing the potential value of the data.

Theoretical Framework

There was a need to first identify appropriate theories that explain why some organisations adopt technologies while others develop a wait-and-see attitude. The following theories appeared to have all the constructs that explained the problem (i) The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) by (Venkatesh, Morris, Davis, & Davis, 2003), (ii) The Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI) (Roger, 2003), and (iii) The Social Exchange Theory (SET) (Homans, Thibout, Blau, & Emerson cited in Emerson, 2008, p. 335).

The UTAUT theory and its constructs that influence the adoption rate are depicted below in Figure 1.

Figure 1

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

Note. Source: Venkatesh et al. (2003)

The theory is built from a combination of 8 theories and has proved to be a very useful theory in the adoption of technologies, and has been used several times by other researchers (Ahmad, 2014). The DOI theory is also used in both the technology field and the commercial field to classify adopters as innovators (2.5%), Early adopters (13.5%), Early Majority (34%), Late Majority (34%), and Laggards (16%) (Roger, 2003). This theory can be used to explain the rate of adoption of big data technologies within the BRICS nations. The SET theory then played the critical role of exchanging data within the BRICS nations, as it involves the social context of exchanging valuables.

Theoretical Assumptions and Engagement of the Three Theories

Big data is driven by technology through the internet and interconnected cyber-physical systems (Khan, Wu, Xu, & Dou, 2017; Da & Duan, 2019; Peres, Jia, Lee, Sun, Colombo, & Barata, 2020). The three theories were used to assess the adoption of big data technologies within the BRICS nations. Do BRICS countries believe that there is value in adopting big data? Is there any relative advantage, “the degree to which an innovation is perceived as better than the idea it supersedes”? By putting big data on its agenda for Internet governance, it shows that BRICS countries believe that adopting big data initiatives will improve their performance (Ignatov, 2022).

The following Figure 2 shows how these three theories complement each other centered on expected benefits.

Figure 2

Engaging the Three Theories on Common Ground

Note. Source: Authors' Construct

The above Figure 2 is useful when exploring what may be hindering BRICS nations from extracting value from the big data environment.

Review of Related Literature on BRICS Digital Policies and Frameworks

Extracting value from big data suits organisations that are in some form of a relationship, where the intended use of data is clearly declared upfront before entering into some form of agreement. This has worked in Australia, where an e-infrastructure was established in 2010 (Sinnott & AURIN-Technical-Team, 2016). This same concept can be adopted by the BRICS. However, this is difficult to implement when country boundaries are crossed because of a lack of clear frameworks (Glosson, 2016) a lack of agreements to address ethics when exchanging the data (Tractenberg et al., 2015).

Therefore, the BRICS countries must immediately address these problems by creating adequate regulations such as regulatory sandboxes (Gromova & Ivanc, 2020; Gondo, Holtman, & Rena, 2023). However, this is being hampered by the fact that some of the member countries do not yet have big data exchange frameworks that promote data exchange in their own country. Those who have crafted laws have come from the data protection angle and not from the data exchange angle. Big data has turned from being the 'new oil' to being a political tool because the approach to extract value from them differ in scope, and governments end up being involved to protect other vulnerable members of society affected by societal changes (Mahrenbach & Mayer, 2020). Countries within the BRICS block have different digital and data control policies/ frameworks.

Brazil

In 2016, the government of Brazil launched the Digital Governance Strategy (EGD). This became a stepping stone towards the central policy of digital transformation, which was configured via the launch of the Gov.br platform aimed to promote big data adoption in Brazil. Then Decree 10,046 created the Central Data Governance Committee (CCGD) to control the usage of data and protect data owners when sharing the data. Congress finally approved the General Data Protection Law (Filgueiras & Lui, 2023). The Brazilian laws aim to promote the sharing of data and at the same time, protect the data. This promotes accountability when extracting value from the big data environment.

Russia

In Russia, there are several data privacy protection laws such as the Federal Service for Technical and Export Control (FSTEC), Federal Security Services (FSS), and the Federal Service for Supervision of Communications, Information Technology, and Mass Communications. All these laws are aimed at protecting citizens, but there is still a feeling that these are still inadequate because the country has no official definition of big data at the legislative level and the IT industry (Konstantinovna & Mikhailovich, 2017). Again, these laws also aim to protect data they do not promote data sharing. The positive move was when the Federal Agency for Technical Regulation and Metrology was developed as a promising standardisation program in the area of Artificial Intelligence to build trust (Kharitonova, Malik, & Yang, 2023).

India

India has had its own fair share of internal challenges with privacy issues in the big environment. The government tried to modernise

the economy through big data by setting up Aadhaar, a unique 12-digit randomly numbered biometric system designed to identify individuals accurately and efficiently. However, this was challenged in the Supreme Court. The ruling aimed at protecting the citizens by highlighting a key issue that India's 1.45 billion citizens had a fundamental right to privacy (Abraham, Bennet, Sen, & Shah, 2018). This triggered celebrations among some citizens, including the opposition leader, who welcomed the ruling as a victory for individuals' freedom, liberty, and dignity (Parajuli, 2017). Indian legislators now focus more on protecting users; however, they do not address the commercial side of digital platforms, which is why new regulations were introduced under the Information Technology Act of 2000 (IT Act). These new regulations were introduced in 2021 as intermediary guidelines and digital media ethics codes (Kharitonova, Malik, & Yang, 2023). They do not promote data sharing.

China

China also launched the Social Credit System (SCS) to try to extract value from the big data. Like the Aadhaar of India, the project was also viewed as controversial, with political and ethical concerns that have attracted media attention. However, media attention in China is lower because the media is somehow controlled by the state (Shahin & Zheng, 2020). Because of their data laws, some of the BRICS countries are labeled as authoritarian regimes, particularly by Western states (Belli & Doneda, 2022). This personal data collection for economic development by China is what Europe sought to challenge through its General Data Protection Regulation Act (GDPR) (Aho & Duffield, 2020). While the SCS has been heavily criticised, similar structures and cultures are now emerging in westernised states to try to extract value from the data (Wong & Dobson, 2019). To promote the development of big data, the state council in China had to issue an action plan that was launched in 2015 (Wu et al., 2020). In 2017, the same state council released the country's strategy for developing Artificial Intelligence to achieve a breakthrough in big data analysis (Roberts et al., 2021; Gondo, Holtman, & Rena, 2023). China has gone further and constructed a data sharing platform that incorporated a series of policies to promote the development of big data; however, data sharing still displays a silo effect (Wu et al., 2020).

South Africa

South Africa is still towards best practises, the cybersecurity and data protection topic has been on the agenda of the South African Government for a long time, with the closest data protection acts being the Protection of Personal Information Act (POPI), which was passed in 2013 and National Cybersecurity Policy Framework (NCPF) (Mabunda, 2019). The South African laws do not promote data sharing; they are more on the data protection side.

Objectives of the Study

- To establish missing elements that are hindering the extraction of value from big data in the current BRICS big data policies/frameworks.
- To develop a suitable framework that can be used by BRICS nations to extract value from the big data riding on their current relationships.

Research Questions

- What elements are missing in the current BRICS big data policies/frameworks and in theories that have dominated big data research?

- What framework would work for the BRICS nations to start extracting value from their big data?

Method

To get a deep understanding of the elements hindering the BRICS block from realising the value of big data, this study first analysed the current frameworks within the BRICS countries. The findings were then fused with the findings from a localised qualitative study that was conducted on 23 participants, which involved technology consultants and the managers as owners of the data, to find out what they want to be addressed first. Though the study was a localised study, it can be applied in the broader scale, such as the BRICS.

Results and Discussion

Discussion of what Emerged from the Literature

By creating the CCGD and approving the General Data Protection Law, the Brazilian Government showed a focus on promoting data sharing in a secure environment. This kind of policy initiative is what is needed on the entire BRICS bloc. The problem with the current policies within the other BRICS countries is that they are aimed at protecting the data and not promoting the sharing of data. This is a direct contradiction to the requirement of extracting value from big data. They seem to focus more on data owned by public institutions, ignoring data owned by the private sector, which is also part of big data. India views big data as a means of improving efficiencies in the public service, and China aims to use big data to improve medical care (Mahrenbach, Mayer, & Pfeffer, 2018). Though BRICS as a block currently face digital policy challenges, once its digital policies take shape, it will affect 2 out of 5 people in the world because BRICS constitute about 40% of existing internet users in the world (Belli, 2020). The models and policies are likely to be considered internationally as post-Western data governance in the future, because three of the BRICS countries are leading in certain aspects of technology, Brazil in the data sharing concept, China in cybersecurity regulation and India in technological expertise (Belli, 2023; Rena, 2024).

Discussion of what Emerged from the Localised Study

In the localised research, managers were asked what they want in place before agreeing to share their data with strategic partners. The question posed to them was aimed at finding out their opinion on exchanging strategic data with key strategic partners. They were also probed to hear their opinion on interconnecting systems to achieve that, and their response was:

“.... First and foremost, we would like assurance that our data is secure and only used for the intended purpose before agreeing to share.”

The above statement shows that data security is one of the most important things that the owners of data consider. They are afraid that sometimes the data may reach the wrong recipients and end up being used to undermine the integrity of the organisation. However, they see no reason why they would not agree to share the data if the legal framework is ready to deal with that. This supports Mahrenbach, Mayer, and Pfeffer's (2018) argument that the controversy around big data is centred on the intended use of the data, particularly when used by the government for surveillance and political gains and not for economic development.

“.....In a normal ideal environment, we don't mind integrating

our internal systems with our key stakeholders as long as the issues of risk, confidentiality and ethical considerations are addressed, I wouldn't mind integrating our systems with our key stakeholders”

This is a clear testimony to show that the technical side has made strides in making it possible to integrate systems and share data. What is now missing are the frameworks to address the above issue. These issues must be declared upfront, and the traditional way is to sign agreements that are enforceable in the court of law in case of any conflict arising from these issues. If such agreements are regulated in a recognised court of law, it would be difficult to breach them. If there is any other way of implementing them electronically in this current big data environment, it will enhance the process.

“.....As you scale up the technology where you link up with your strategic partner; there is a need to sign Memorandum of Understanding (MOUs), Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDA) with your partners to say, the data are for you only, you cannot share them with other external people”.

Therefore, there is a need to have some privacy policies in place to guide and control the exchange of data due to an increase in cybersecurity crimes that sometimes breach security protocols. The best way would be to share the data using proper secure application platforms that are robust, developed to address those concerns (1) provide secure interfaces, (2) allow data encryption, and (3) have an audit trail to show who accessed what, when accessed, and what was accessed.

“...Organisations only get targeted specific data from external sources they do not take everything to avert the risk associated with getting external data”.

The above statement shows that, though the big data environment comprises large volumes of data sets, users of data in the environment do not look for every piece of data; they look for specific data that addresses their needs. Therefore, the data must be shared with specific partners who are in the same domain of interest. As for the BRICS, those in tourism can have their node where they can exchange data on advancing tourism within the BRICS, those in research, health, construction, education, and government also have their own domain each, where they share data of that domain. That way, the domains will form their own big data value chains that then form the BRICS big data platform. A framework to extract value from that big data environment can then be designed. The same concept has worked very well for the Australian Urban Research Infrastructure Network (AURIN), where they are now extracting value from the big data using interrelated datasets of particular interest to Australian Urban researchers, such as health, housing, transport, population, and many more (Sinnott & AURIN-Technical-Team, 2016b). The AURIN concept has been used in several other studies in the last decade (Bassiri Abyaneh et al., 2023).

“....It would have to be more of a leader of one entity going to the leader of the other to discuss the sharing of data to everyone's mutual benefit either up the value chain or down the value chain so there is a need to identify the value chain of entities that would benefit then investment in similar technologies that allow data communication between those entities.”.

The above statement shows that there is need for an initiative from the leaders (owners of data) to discuss the value of data sharing. For BRICS, the data first belongs to individuals, private companies, and public institutions of each country within the BRICS. Therefore, to

extract value from the BRICS big data, the leaders of these institutions must first identify the data they have in their operations, then engage their peers within their value chain with an idea of sharing data. However, this is impossible if there are no proper communication channels, laws and frameworks that guide the process of exchanging data, especially if it crosses country boundaries. Currently, organisations are aware of the benefits of exchanging data for mutual benefit however, from the above analysis, they are still hesitant to share data. From individuals, companies to Governments everyone is trying to protect their own territory. However, from this study, it has emerged that if the platform is designed properly with proper security and authorisation levels, it should work.

Summary of what Emerged from this Study

What emerged from this study is that, though technology, through the hardcore sciences, is at the forefront of driving the emerging big data field by creating the data and the platform for storing and exchanging data. Social sciences control and govern the usage of the resultant data.

Figure 3

The Five V's of Big Data and Focus Area

Note. Source: Authors' construct

The above diagram shows the 5 V's of big data in relation to focus areas. Volume and velocity put pressure on hardware and the network, and this is the focus area of hardcore sciences. Variety is also their focus area because it also puts pressure on the databases, as unstructured data cannot be handled easily, the way it is done with traditional relational databases. This has seen the need to explore other emerging databases, such as Hadoop, to address the issue. This is also the same with veracity, which refers to data full of uncertainty, which may require the development of algorithms to address the issue.

On the other hand, social sciences, management, health, administration, and other fields focus on using the data to get insights and extract value. To achieve those objectives, they want access to a variety of data sources. They also want to deal with data that is full of uncertainty.

For the BRICS block, it is now time to address data usage by fusing technology and social sciences to address the big data issue.

There is still a lack of a theoretical framework to help organisations to realise the full potential presented by the abundance of data in other fields of study, such as health (Jia et al., 2020). Hence, there is a need to have new theoretical lenses to look at the current factors hindering the extraction of value from the big data environment.

What dominated this piece of work is the security concern to handle the data in an accountable manner that addresses risk and ethical issues. These elements must therefore be incorporated into the UTAUT theory to start adopting the big data initiatives in organisations within the BRICS. This is shown in the following Figure 4.

Figure 4

Proposed Modification to the UTAUT Theory for Big Data Adoption

Note. Adapted from Source: (Williams, Rana, & Dwivedi, 2015, p.444)

What the authors of this study suggest as amendments to the UTAUT theory. The three elements that could be added are shown in red in the above diagram. If these elements are not addressed, organisations will continue to be hesitant to adopt big data initiatives. The benefits may be known, but these will be overshadowed by the fact that these elements are missing. There is a need to first come up with a clear legal framework before exchanging data because the big issue that has affected the adoption of big data is the lack of a clear framework (Olszak & Mach-Król, 2018).

This study proposes the following framework for the BRICS.

Figure 5

Proposed BRICS Big Data Adoption Framework

Note. Source: Authors' construct

The above figure is the proposed framework that the BRICS nations can use to realise value from big data. Using BRICS people-to-people relationship cluster domains with similar information needs can be formed, for example, under tourism, air transport, education, health, construction and many more. Ministerial task forces can be used to spearhead the development of these big data domains and agree on a code of ethics to exchange the data. The initial domains can be formed at country level and then join the BRICS cluster for that specific domain. Input from these subdomains can then be used to come up with the consolidated BRICS main domain, which can then become the BRICS big data regulatory framework. BRICS should then invest in appropriate infrastructure such as cloud computing to support the sub-domains and the consolidated BRICS domain. This kind of initiative is only possible in countries that are in some form of relationship and can be used to improve the lives of their people.

Implications of what Emerged from the Study on the BRICS Policy Makers

BRICS as a block may need to come up with a data regulating inter-ministerial committee that oversees the crafting of data exchange law to regulate the exchange of data between entities within the BRICS group.

Conclusion

This research study provided a framework that can be used by the BRICS for the purpose of adopting big data. It proposed the use of using focus area clusters as a means of grouping users with different information needs to enable them to realise the value hidden in big data. It also proposed modifications to the UTAUT theory and put forward suggestions on how the elements of trust, risk and ethical consideration that dominate the social side should be used to address both the technological and the social aspects in adoption of big data by BRICS. This is because technology generates the data and society uses the data hence, the two, go hand in hand.

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